

THE IMPORTANCE OF THEIR AGE-RELATED PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN THE PROCESS OF SCHOOL CHILDREN'S LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

One of the characteristics of educational activities as the social status of Junior Secondary School student development and primary school age leadership activities is also associated with their psychology. In the structure of educational activities, of course, it is necessary that the level of psychological development of children also coincide with the requirements of educational activities. Cognitive development and cognitive development of children of primary school age are considered important.

The features of the development of attention, memory and speech of young students, as well as their mental development, are also part of the psychology of students. One of the main directions of the formation of intelligence in children of small school age is their self-confidence. It is necessary to stimulate the mental development of schoolchildren at a young age. Through the formation of the personality of the pupil at a young age and their self-assessment, both psychologists are learned. The developmental characteristics of the will also begin with the early school age of the students. In this article, opinions and comments are made on the importance of their age-related psychological characteristics in the educational system in the process of schoolchildren's education.

INTRODUCTION.

Personal reflection. At school age, the number of self-respecting factors increases significantly. Children at the age of 9 to 12 years continue to form a desire that everything has its own point of view. They also have judgments about their social significance - self-esteem. It develops due to the development of self-awareness and reflection on those who value their thoughts. High scores usually occur in children when parents are treated with interest, warmth and love. However, by the age of 12-13 years the child will have a new idea, self-esteem will lose its attachment to cases of success-failure, but will have a stable character. Self-esteem now represents a relationship in which the image of oneself symbolizes an ideal self.

Small school age is the completion of self-awareness. This means reflection from the point of view of thinking. The child begins

to think about the reasons why he thinks so, and not otherwise. There is a mechanism for correcting one's own thinking from Logic, theoretical knowledge. Consequently, the child is able to subjugate the intention of a reasonable goal, be able to hold it for a long time. During school years, the ability to store and retrieve information from memory improves and develops. Children not only remember better, but they also think about how to do it.

Mental development. 7 - 11 years, intellect the third period of development is the period of clear thinking. The child's thinking is limited to problems with certain real objects. That is, the egocentrism inherent in children's gradually decreases, which is facilitated by joint games, but does not disappear completely. Especially often children make mistakes, guess the result. As a result, the children who formulated the hypothesis, without changing their point of view, reject the new ones. In place of decentralization, the ability to simultaneously pay attention to several attributes, correlate them, simultaneously take into account several dimensions of the state of an object or phenomenon arises. The child also develops the ability to intelligently observe changes in the object.

In the process of education in primary school students, scientific concepts are formed. Very important influence on the formation of verbal-logical thinking, they do not appear in the "space". In order to learn them, children should be sufficiently developed everyday concepts - ideas, which are of preschool age and each child will continue to appear on their own, based on his or her own experience. The Daily concept is the lower concentration level,

scientific-higher, higher, awareness and self-esteem. In the process of mastering scientific consciousness goes from generalization to concrete objects. The skill of learning the system of scientific concepts makes it possible to speak the basics of conjectural or theoretical thinking about the development in primary school children. Theoretical thinking allows the student to solve problems, is guided not by external, concrete signs and relations of objects, but by internal, important properties and relationships. The development of other mental functions depends on the development of thinking. If preschool children are characterized by an analysis of perception, by the end of primary school age, there is a synthesizing perception with appropriate training. The secondary school student is included in the educational activities of social significance, the results of which are evaluated by close adults at a high or low level. The assessment of a child from school activities as a good or bad pupil directly depends on the development of his personality during this period.

METHODOLOGY AND OBJECTIVES.

The motivational sphere is the core of the individual. At the beginning of school life, having an internal position of the student, he wants to learn. And well, learn perfectly. Among the various social reasons for education, perhaps the most important role is occupied by the motifs of obtaining higher grades. A high rating for a small student is another source of motivation, a guarantee of his emotional well - being, a matter of pride. An important aspect of cognitive motivation is learning and cognitive motivations, the reasons for self-improvement. If the child has learned

something in the educational process, understood, learned that happy, then he develops motivation corresponding to the structure of the educational activity.

Children with low and low self-esteem often experience a feeling of embarrassment and even frustration. The reduce the seriousness of these experiences, compensation motivation-attention is focused not on educational activities, but on other activities. But even in cases where children are covered by poor performance with achievements in other areas, there are negative consequences - "muffled" deficiency, a sense of inferiority, acceptance of a position of apathy. For children to develop feelings of self-esteem and psychological comfort and competence necessary to create an atmosphere of support class. Becoming a junior student self-esteem depends not only on his performance and the characteristics of the teacher communication with the class. Of great importance is the style of Family Education, adopting family value. School and family are external factors of the development of self-consciousness. Its formation depends on the development of the child's theoretical reflexive thinking. By the end of the elementary school age there is a reflection, thus creating new opportunities for self-esteem achievements and the construction of personal qualities. Self-esteem is usually more adequate and differentiated judgment about themselves-more reasonable. At the same time, there are wide individual differences here. It should be noted that children with high and low self-esteem change its level is very difficult.

A look at the 7-year crisis of psychology. The turning point in the life of each child is the crisis of 7-year-old children. This period is characterized by certain symptoms, not always pleasant for parents. Psychology has been studying the issue for many decades and has made some progress. At this age, children should act like adults, dress like adults, decide for themselves. The development of such demand is facilitated mainly by the growing cultural environment of children. Even from an early age, going to the first class, it will mature and become very adult. Therefore, he wants to take on the post of a new social schoolboy. *Causes and symptoms of the crisis.* After the young crisis played an important role in the formation of personality, and as a result appeared a mental tumor, on which it will develop in the future. This applies to any kind of young crisis. One of the most important psychological tumors 7 years-is the need for social activity. Age Physiology also implies change (change of deciduous teeth, active growth, etc.). Psychologists determine that the main cause of the crisis is the personal development of the child as well as the emergence of self-knowledge. The crisis has its manifestations: Loss of self-esteem. Children begin to think about the meaning of each of his actions before you commit it. Childhood is lost. When the child begins to act hard and to seem smart, secrets must appear in it from parents. Copying adult behavior is exemplary in this theater and for the first time. At the age of 7, the child tries to hide from adults when he is bad.

The beginning of the crisis and the steps it is necessary to distinguish between primary school and preschool age (3 7 years) in the field of child psychology

specialists. It is believed that during this period the child begins to think about the meaning of the work and its pleasure or dissatisfaction. In other words, children have the basics of trying emotional and semantic orientation. Relationships with adults. The behavior and development of children is influenced by the style of leadership of adults: authoritarian, democratic or conniving (anarchist). Children feel better and develop more successfully under the leadership of democracy.

DISCUSSES AND RESULTS.

In favorable conditions, in education and on this basis, at a sufficient level of intellectual development, there are necessary conditions for the development of theoretical thinking and consciousness. At this age, the child first begins to understand the reasons for social behavior, moral evaluation, the importance of conflict situations, begins to clearly understand the relationship between him and others, gradually entering the conscious stage of the formation of equality. Psychological characteristics of a young student :

1. The crisis is the period of the birth of the social "I" of a 7-year-old child. Features of the crisis: a reassessment of values, a generalization of experience, the emergence of a child's inner life, a semantic framework aimed at Action, determined by the loss of childhood.

2. Social status of development in early school years. The development set a new social situation with the child enters the school. The center of the state of social development becomes a pedagogue. Their

psychology is adversely affected by social stratification.

3. Educational activity-as a leader activity. Thus, the young leader in primary school becomes an educational activity. Educational activity is a special form of student activity aimed at changing yourself as a subject of study. Each activity is characterized by its subject. For the first time the subject of educational activity is confused with itself, it changes in the course of its work or "in itself".

Relationships with peers. From the age of six, children increasingly spend time with their peers, almost always with the same sex. Compliance has been increasing, reaching its peak by 12 years. Popular children usually adapt well, feel comfortable among peers and are usually able to cooperate. One game. Children still devote a lot of time to the game. In it, Feelings of cooperation and competition develop, such concepts as justice and injustice, treason, Equality, Leadership, subordination, loyalty, betrayal acquire personal meaning. The game takes on social coloring: children invent secret societies, clubs, secret cards, encryptions, passwords and special rituals. The role and rules of the children's society make it possible to master the rules adopted in adult society. Games with friends between the ages of 6 and 11 require the most time.

Emotional development. From the moment the child goes to school, his emotional development depends on the experience that he has more outside the home than before. The child's fears reflect the perception of the environment, its scale is now. The inexplicable and imaginary fear of previous years is replaced by others,

more conscious: lessons, injections, natural phenomena, relations between peers. Fear can take the form of anxiety or anxiety.

The first comp in educational activities is motivation. Educational activities are politically motivated - it is interrelated and sent with various educational motivations. Among them are the motivations that best fit the educational tasks; if they are formulated by the student, his / her academic work will be meaningful and effective. That is, they call the reasons for learning and knowledge. They are based on the need for knowledge and the need for self-development. This is an interest in the content side of educational activity, what is being studied, and interest in the process of activity-through what, by what means, the results will be achieved. The child should be encouraged not only by the result, but also in the process of learning activities. This is also a self-improvement, which is a reason for their growth, the development of one's abilities. The second component-learning task, that is, the system of tasks, in which the child learns the most common methods of action. Children solve many specific tasks and open for themselves a common way to solve them for themselves. Initially, the work of teaching children is supervised by the teacher. But gradually they begin to control it in part by themselves, partly by studying it under the guidance of the teacher. Without self-control, it is impossible to place educational activities in full force. Development of mental functions. In the early school years, the dominant feature becomes a way of thinking. As a result of this, the thinking processes are intensively developing and restoring, on the other hand, the development of other mental functions depends on the mind.

Preschool transition from visual-figurative to verbal and logical thinking ends explained. A logical reasoning appears in the child: reasoning, using the operation. However, this is not a formal-logical operation, a small schoolboy can not yet meditate hypothetically.

Thus, according to psychologists, the crisis is the necessary conditions for the development of the individual. There are two types of age: stable and critical. An important period for people is rapid development. This period is characterized by a lack of harmony between the child and his environment, in addition, at this time there is a breakdown of old and new ideas about the world and himself. What changes in child psychology - however, we encounter the opposite opinion of psychologists. Parental mistakes are an expression, and scientists consider it a crisis. This significant moment is primarily associated with the change in the passage of games for the study of basic activities (based on which new goals appear in life. As you can see, even in the context of child psychology, there is no consensus as to the crisis in relation to such a period in life. And parents for himself must decide to fight him with a naughty child.

How hard are their parents waiting? So try to understand what parents can face and how to overcome the crisis. Entering the difficult period of life of the child at the age of 7 years, the child is not in the first grade, his social environment is changing his duties and daily habits. Parents think that their obedient child will become very strong and will begin to withdraw into himself and begin to clean yourself up to build a laughing stock. In psychology specialists, in 7 years, children develop a

social "I", which leads to a change in behavior. But what does it mean? There is a change in interests, that is, the game is no longer interested in it, it is now its main job to learn, evaluate and become a success. The Preschooler is aware of himself as a separate independent person with his own feelings and experiences and tries to show them as much as possible, and there is theatrical behavior and antics. Parents may be faced with the fact that their son or daughter does not want to go to school. But what is the reason? they are afraid that the impression of adult conversations in children waiting for him in school, very difficult. In addition, many children have a thirst for learning and a desire to learn to read and write, and even the kindergarten is partially satisfied.

The child begins to realize that he is an individual who is subject to social influences: the development of the individual at a young school age developing accelerated self-consciousness in early school years. At this age, self-awareness and self-reflection as the ability to set their own limits to reflect on their own opportunities manifests itself in the ability to distinguish characteristics of their own actions from developing and do, and their object of analysis is very important that the child knows how he can and really knows, the best ability for young students to The importance of Free goals in the task of optimal complexity for the development of the will of young learners is very light or volitional regulation of the problems of the child sees his progress towards the goal, whereas the development of volitional qualities and the inhibition of the conditions of the will of the devel of strength and the formation.

CONCLUSIONS.

In conclusion, by the end of the primary school age, strong-willed character traits such as Independence, perseverance, endurance are formed. At this age, the assimilation of moral norms and rules of conduct will be: the child shows attention to the moral side of behavior in public places, masters are more accurate in their behavior and understand the norms of behavior in different houses. Thus, children's emotions change its expressive side, the emotional sphere serves as a more general, arbitrary, social arrangement, complex. Motivation at the end of primary school age is a deep motivational crisis, which is associated with the desire to obtain a new social position for education, tired and meaningful reasons, in the age of 8-10 years. Young school age is characterized by a person aged 6-7 years to 10-11 years of age, high sensitivity, hospitality, self-esteem, internal plan of action, self-control and reflection. Primary School Age covers the period from 6 to 11 years of age and is determined by the most important factor in a child's life - his or her entry into school. This is an improvement in the formation of cognitive processes (perception, memory, attention), higher mental functions (speech, writing, reading, counting), which allows a child of primary school age to produce more complex, already compared with preschool, mental operations. In favorable conditions, in education and on this basis, at a sufficient level of intellectual development, there are necessary conditions for the development of theoretical thinking and consciousness. At this age, the child first begins to understand the reasons for social behavior, moral evaluation, the importance of conflict situations, begins to clearly

understand the relationship between him and others, gradually entering the

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